

ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC AND POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF MIRZO ULUGBEK

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Mirzo Ulugbek: Outstanding scholar and ruler of the Middle Ages Mirzo Ulugbek (1394-1449) is a monumental figure, combining the talents of a scientist-encyclopedic, mathematician, astronomer, educator and poet, as well as a wise ruler. Being the grandson of the famous conqueror Tamerlane, he ruled Maverannahr from 1409, leaving a deep trace in the history of both his epoch and subsequent centuries. Mirzo Ulugbek and his Political Role in the Context of the Middle Ages. Mirzo Ulugbek, in addition to his outstanding scientific achievements, was a significant figure in the political arena of the Middle Ages. During his reign from 1409 to 1449, he led the vast Timurid Empire, covering the territories of present-day Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Iran, Afghanistan and other countries. His political activity was characterized by the following aspects: Strengthening centralized power and ensuring internal stability. Ulugbek introduced administrative reforms, improved the taxation system and strengthened the army. These measures allowed him to consolidate his power and ensure the peaceful development of the empire. Active foreign policy. Ulugbek sought to strengthen the international prestige of his state. He established diplomatic relations with many countries around the world, including China, India, and the Ottoman Empire.

He also made a number of military campaigns, increasing the territory of his empire. Patronage of science and culture. Ulugbek was not only a talented ruler, but also an outstanding scientist. Mirzo Ulugbek's contribution to trigonometry. Description of his works on development of new trigonometric methods. Analyzing his contribution to the creation of tables of sines and tangents. A comparison of his achievements in trigonometry with those of other mathematicians of the time. Mirzo

Ulugbek's studies in geometry. Description of his works on the study of Euclidean geometry and spherical trigonometry. Analysis of his contribution to solving problems of geometry and astronomy. Comparison of his achievements in geometry with those of other mathematicians of that time. Significance of Mirzo Ulugbek's mathematical works for the development of mathematical science. Description of the influence of his works on subsequent mathematicians. Analysis of the use of his methods and tables in various fields of science. Evaluation of his contribution to the formation of the foundations of modern mathematics. History of Science.

"We owe the discovery of the observatory location to a waqf document I found, written about 250 years ago, in which the observatory hill ("tal-i-rasad") and the Abi-Rahmat ditch and the area of Naqsh-i-Jahan, now known by the same names, are among the described boundaries of the land plot. This document gave such precise and quite definite indications on the location of the observatory that it was not difficult to find the hill mentioned in the document" [1.76 p], - wrote V.L. Vyatkin in his report on the excavations of Mirzo Ulugbek's observatory, published in 1912. After the establishment of Soviet power in Turkestan, V.L. Vyatkin, along with other duties, continued to work on the protection of monuments of Samarkand and was elected chairman of the Samarkand Committee for Museums and Protection of Monuments of Antiquity, Art Nature, which was part of the Committee for Museums and Protection of Monuments of Antiquity, Art Nature of the Turkestan ASSR. All researchers who came to Samarkand on archaeological, historical architectural expeditions or for any other scientific purpose, first of all, turned to Vasily Lavrentievich Vyatkin, as he was the leading expert on the monuments of Samarkand.

Mirzo Ulugbek founded, in Samarkand one of the largest observatories of the Middle Ages, equipped with advanced instruments of the time. He compiled a star catalog "Zij Ulugbek" containing information about 1018 stars with accuracy ahead of its time. He determined the duration of the sidereal year with a record accuracy at that time. He made a significant contribution to the study of the motion of planets, comets and, other celestial bodies. He wrote treatises on trigonometry and algebra that enriched the science of mathematics. He contributed to the development of spherical trigonometry, important for astronomical calculations. His mathematical work was ahead of the achievements of European scientists of the time. Assessment of his importance as one of the key figures in the history of science of the Middle Ages. Mirzo Ulugbek's legacy for future generations of scientists. Description of his works as a source of knowledge and inspiration for subsequent scholars. Analyzing the use of his methods and ideas in various fields of science. Evaluating his contribution to the formation of scientific worldview. In addition to these main

topics, one can also explore. Mirzo Ulugh Beg's influence on architecture and art. Describing his role in the construction of monumental structures in Samarkand. Analyzing his support for poets, painters and other artists. Evaluation of his contribution to the development of culture of the Middle Ages. Personality and world outlook of Mirzo Ulugbek.

A description of his education, interests and hobbies. Analyses of his political activities and diplomatic relations. Evaluation of his role as a wise ruler and enlightened leader. The study of Mirzo Ulugbek's scientific heritage allows. Deepen understanding of the history of science and culture of the Middle Ages. Evaluate the contribution of one of the greatest scientists and rulers of his time. Be inspired by his pursuit of knowledge and his achievements in various fields. Contribution to education. He founded madrasas in Samarkand, Bukhara, Gijduvan, which became center's of science and education in Maverannahr. Invited the best scholars of his time to teach in his madrasas. He established scholarships for students from different countries, encouraging the influx of talented students. It was on his initiative that in 1918 a commission was formed, including engineers M.F. Mauer and B.N. Kastalsky, to provide "emergency aid [1. P.93] " to the north-eastern minaret of the madrasah, built in 1417-1420 by Mirzo Ulugbek [1. P.93]. Mirzo Ulugbek [4. P.16]. The State Archive of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the personal collection of V.L. Vyatkin [6] has preserved many documents, protocols, letters, appeals, testifying to the enormous practical and scientific efforts that were made to preserve the current appearance of Registan Square in Samarkand at a difficult time for Uzbekistan.

As M.E. Masson wrote, "the members of the commission were clearly aware that the famous Ulugh Beg Madrasah is a monument of great scientific and artistic importance, and that its main facade without one corner minaret will be unacceptably disfigured", because without it in 1870, one of the four minarets of the madrasah collapsed, and later the second one. Almost every meeting of the commission, some of which took place right on Registan Square, was accompanied by heated debates on the issue of the quickest possible rescue and straightening of the minaret of the madrasah. The work was carried out during the 1918 - 1932 and was completed successfully. It was an unprecedented case in the world history of restoration practice. Along with his official duties and research work directly in Samarkand, V.L. Vyatkin was repeatedly sent to different regions of Uzbekistan by Sredazkomstaris to conduct archaeological excavations and survey of architectural monuments of the region with all the powers related to his activities [6]. Wherever he worked, he always returned to his native Samarkand. Judging by one archival document, V.L. Vyatkin preferred to do most of his official and scientific work at home. Mirzo Ulugbek created an education system based on meritocracy, where

knowledge and talent were valued above origin. Ulugbek's activities stimulated the development of science and culture in Maverannahr, turning it into one of the center's of enlightenment in the 15th century.

His works on astronomy and mathematics influenced the development of these sciences in Europe. Ulugbek left a rich scientific and cultural legacy that is still studied and appreciated by scientists around the world. Ulugbek's Zij was translated into Latin and was used by European astronomers for several centuries. Ulugbek patronized poets and artists, which contributed to the flourishing of art in Maverannahr. Architectural monuments built on Ulugbek's orders, such as the Ulugbek Madrasah in Samarkand, are still admired for their beauty and grandeur. According to legend, as a child Ulugbek had the opportunity to visit the ruins of the famous observatory of At-Tusi, Nasir ad-Din in Maragha. This made a strong impression on the inquisitive Ulugbek and determined his passion for astronomy. Under Ulugbek, Samarkand became one of the world centers of science of the Middle Ages. Here, in Samarkand in the first half of the 15th century, a whole scientific school emerged around Ulugbek, uniting prominent astronomers and mathematicians - Giyasiddin Jamshid Kashi, Kazizade Rumi, al-Kushchi. The historian Hafizi Abru, who wrote a remarkable work on the history of Central Asia, the famous physician Mavlono Nafis, poets Sirajiddin Samarkandi, Sakkaki, Lutfi, Badakhshi and others lived in Samarkand at that time.

Ulugbek's main interest in science was astronomy. In 1428 the construction of Ulugbek's observatory was completed, the main instrument of which was a wall quadrant with a radius of 40 metres and with a working part from 20° to 80° , to which there was no equal. Such outstanding astronomers as Kazi-zade al-Rumi, al-Kashi and al-Kushchi were Ulugbek's collaborators. In Ulugbek's observatory by 1437, Gurgan zij, a catalogue of the starry sky, was compiled, in which 1018 stars were described. The length of the stellar year was also determined there: 365 days, 6 hours, 10 minutes, 8 seconds (with an error of + 58 seconds) and the tilt of the Earth's axis: 23.52° (the most accurate measurement) [3].

Mirzo Ulugbek's contribution to the star catalogue "Zij Ulugbek". Description of the methodology of creation of the catalogue, its accuracy and significance. Comparative analysis of "Zij Ulugbek" with other star catalogues of that time. Influence of "Zij Ulugbek" on development of astronomy in Europe and in the East. Mirzo Ulugbek's researches of planets' motion. Description of his methods for determining the orbits of the planets, including the use of the astrolabe. Analysing his contribution to the understanding of the precession of the Earth's axis and nutation. Comparing his achievements in the study of the planets with those of other astronomers of the time. The role of Ulugbek's observatory in the development of

astronomical observations. Description of the design and equipment of the observatory. Analysis of the contribution of the observatory to the improvement of astronomical instruments. Significance of Ulugbek's observatory as a centre of astronomical research in the Middle Ages. The main scientific work of Ulugbek is rightly considered to be "Ziji jadidi Guragani" or "New Guragani Astronomical Tables". The author completed this work in 1444 after thirty years of painstaking work and astronomical observations. The astronomical handbook was soon translated into Latin and along with "Almagest" by Claudius Ptolemy and astronomical tables of Castilian king Alfonso was a manual on astronomy in all observatories of Europe [3].

The accuracy of these tables exceeded everything previously achieved in the East and in Europe. It was not until the 17th century that Tycho Brahe managed to achieve comparable accuracy with the Samarkand observations, and then surpassed it. It is not surprising that Ulugbek's Zij constantly attracted the attention of astronomers both in the East and in Europe. The establishment of the Samarkand observatory was possible because in the person of Ulugh Beg the most important components of success came together: a talented scientist who had a clear idea of the scientific goal and ways of its realisation and the ruler of a powerful state who had sufficient funds. The most important result of the Samarkand school is considered to be a catalog of stars. In the East such catalogues were called zijas. The preceding star catalog were apparently based on the observations of Hipparchus, brought to the appropriate epoch. "Ulugbek's zij was largely based on his own observations. Ulugbek was a great patron of science and the arts. Besides astronomy and geography, he was fond of poetry and history. Perhaps, the author of the historical work "History of the Four Ulus" ("*Tarikh-i arba ulus*") was Ulugbek himself [2 p. 88.]. From 1427 to 1447 Ulugbek practically did not conduct any serious military actions. In 1428 he carried out an important monetary reform in the country, which had a favorable impact on the economy of the state.

The organization of higher education and the founding of the Ulugh Beg Madrasah in Gijduvan, Bukhara province of Uzbekistan Ulugh Beg Madrasah in Bukhara, Uzbekistan Ulugh Beg Madrasah in Samarkand, Uzbekistan. Continuing the policy of his grandfather Timur, Ulugbek took care of the development of higher education in the country. In 1417-1420 Ulugbek built a madrasah in Samarkand , which became the first building in the architectural ensemble Registan. In this madrasah Ulugbek invited a large number of astronomers and mathematicians of the Islamic world. The other two madrasahs were built in Gijduvan and Bukhara. An inscription (ahadith of the Prophet Muhammad) is preserved on the portal of the latter: "The pursuit of knowledge is the duty of every Muslim and Muslim woman".

In general, all the numerous inscriptions on the madrasas encourage people to pursue the sciences. He considered the removal of tiles from the buildings of the Shah-i-Zinda ensemble by the tsarist administration to store them in the Stieglitz Museum in St. Petersburg to be no less gross violation of the rights of Turkestanis and cultural sanctimony and wrote with indignation: "... What feeling will be caused in Muslims by the abuse of their holy shrine, which attracts pilgrims every day even from distant places? Do we have the right to arouse this feeling? Finally, one will take away the doors, another the grave stone, a third the paneling from the dome of buildings, a fourth will wish to drag Tamerlane's tomb and the end of this plunder can only come when there is nothing left to drag.

We hope that not only assistance, but also permission will not follow for such a shameful for us deed as barbaric mutilation of the artistic heritage inherited to us from former times" [7]. [7]. Being the caretaker of Samarkand monuments, from year to year he was in constant correspondence with administrative bodies, requesting the allocation of funds for the repair and restoration of this or that historical building. V.L. Vyatkin did not limit himself to appealing to administrative bodies and not waiting for an answer, he also sought help among local businessmen and craftsmen [8]. Another appeal of V.L. Vyatkin concerned the Mirzo Ulugbek madrasah, the rescue and preservation of which has a long and long history, and its beginning, as it turned out when studying the personal fund of Vasily Vyatkin, did not begin in 1918, as noted in his brochure by M.E. Masson [5].

Conclusion. Mirzo Ulugbek is one of the greatest scientists and rulers of the Middle Ages. His contribution to the development of science, education and culture is enormous. His name still remains a symbol of enlightenment, wisdom and pursuit of knowledge. Mirzo Ulugbek – Light-bearing ruler and scientist. Mirzo Ulugbek is undoubtedly one of the greatest scientists and rulers of the Middle Ages. His enormous contribution to the development of astronomy, mathematics and other sciences has left an indelible mark on history. In addition to his scientific achievements, Ulugbek was a wise and far-sighted ruler who cared about the welfare of his people. He patronized scientists, poets, artists and builders, striving to make his country a center of science and culture. Thanks to his activities, Samarkand became one of the most important cultural centers of the Islamic world. Mirzo Ulugbek remains a model for future generations, inspiring by his pursuit of knowledge, wisdom and justice. His name continues to be honored around the world and his legacy continues to influence the development of science and culture. It is important to remember and appreciate the contribution of this great man to world civilization.

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